

ViSketch-GPT: Collaborative Multi-Scale Feature Extraction for Hand-Drawn Sketch Retrieval

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Abstract. Understanding the nature of hand-drawn sketches is challenging due to the wide variation in their creation. Federico et al. (Federico, Amato, Carrara, Gennaro and Di Benedetto (2025)) demonstrated that recognizing complex structural patterns enhances both sketch recognition and generation. Building on this foundation, we explore how the extracted features can also be leveraged for **hand-drawn sketch retrieval**. In this work, we extend **ViSketch-GPT**, a multi-scale context extraction model originally designed for classification and generation, to the task of retrieval. The model’s ability to capture intricate details at multiple scales allows it to learn highly discriminative representations, making it well-suited for retrieval applications.

Through extensive experiments on the QuickDraw and TU-Berlin datasets, we show that ViSketch-GPT **surpasses state-of-the-art methods** in sketch retrieval, achieving substantial improvements across multiple evaluation metrics. Our results show that the extracted feature representations, originally designed for classification and generation, are also highly effective for retrieval tasks. This highlights ViSketch-GPT as a versatile and high-powerful framework for various applications in computer vision and sketch analysis.

Keywords: Sketch. Retrieval. Generative AI. AI. LLM. DDPM. Signed Distance Function. Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Hand-drawn sketches have long been studied across diverse fields such as art, cognitive science, and computer vision. They represent fast and spontaneous visual expressions, often created to convey an idea, concept, or emotion. Due to their inherent variability and subjectivity — shaped by individual perception, artistic style, and intent — understanding and interpreting sketches remains a highly challenging task. Unlike structured forms of visual data such as photographs, diagrams, technical drawings, or maps that adhere to consistent conventions, sketches exhibit significant variability in style, detail, quality, and abstraction. This variability often reflects the creator’s personal interpretation or creative intention rather than strict visual norms.

For instance, datasets like QuickDraw (Ha and Eck, 2018) contain a large volume of sketches but of relatively low quality—often noisy, ambiguous, or heavily abstracted—leading to significant intra-class variability. In contrast, the TU-Berlin dataset (Eitz, Hays and Alexa, 2012), though much smaller, consists of cleaner, more representative sketches that consistently reflect the intended category. This contrast underscores the need for new mechanisms capable of capturing the full complexity of sketches and effectively applying it to downstream tasks such as generation, classification or retrieval.

Federico et al. (Federico et al. (2025)) introduced a novel architecture designed to model sketch complexity through collaborative multi-scale feature extraction called **ViSketch-GPT**. The model outperforms existing state-of-the-art performance in both sketch generation and classification. In this new study, we investigate the adaptability of this architecture to a different downstream task: sketch retrieval. Our results demonstrate that the proposed framework is not only flexible but also effective in this setting, **outperforming state-of-the-art results** on both highly variable and curated sketch datasets, demonstrating robustness across extreme differences in style and quality.

2 Background and Related Works

Previous research on freehand drawings has primarily represented sketches in a pixel-based format and leveraged convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for their interpretation. Following the introduction of Sketch-a-Net in 2015 (Yu, Yang, Song, Xiang and Hospedales, 2015), a pioneering CNN-based model for free-hand sketch generation, the field has experienced significant advancements in neural architectures, data representations, and sketch datasets. Subsequent work explored vector-based representations of sketches, motivated by their inherently sequential nature. In 2017, Google launched QuickDraw, a large-scale dataset containing over 50 million user-submitted sketches, and introduced SketchRNN (Ha and Eck, 2018), an RNN-based Variational Autoencoder capable of handling diverse and expressive sketches. However, the learned representations were primarily tailored for generative tasks rather than recognition or retrieval. To this end, Sketch-BERT (Lin, Fu, Xue and Jiang, 2020), inspired by the BERT architecture (Devlin, Chang, Lee and Toutanova, 2019), treats sketches as sequences of vector strokes, drawing an analogy to how sentences are processed in natural language processing. It adapts the transformer model to operate over sketch data, where each token corresponds to a drawing segment encoded with spatial coordinates and pen states (pen down, pen up, end of sketch). After undergoing a pre-training phase (Sketch Gestalt), the model is fine-tuned for sketch retrieval. During this stage, it learns to produce feature embeddings specifically optimized to distinguish between different sketches for retrieval tasks.

Ideally, one could move beyond the dichotomy between raster and vector representations by leveraging both the visual and sequential nature of sketches, aiming to obtain richer representations better suited for discriminative tasks such as retrieval. This perspective aligns with the growing interest in Sketch-

Based Image Retrieval (SBIR) (Bhunia, Chowdhury, Sain, Yang, Xiang and Song, 2021; Bhunia, Koley, Khilji, Sain, Chowdhury, Xiang and Song, 2022; Chaudhuri, Mancini, Chen, Akata and Dutta, 2022; Dey, Riba, Dutta, Lladós and Song, 2019; Dutta and Akata, 2020), and more broadly, content retrieval based on free-hand drawings. Furthermore, it is emerging as a versatile and inclusive mode of visual interaction. In scenarios where linguistic barriers or vocabulary limitations hinder precise verbal descriptions — for instance, when non-native speakers attempt to search for specific objects they are unable to name — sketches serve as a powerful medium of universal expression. In this context, sketch retrieval not only facilitates access to visual content but also supports a more natural, intuitive, and accessible form of communication among individuals from diverse linguistic or cultural backgrounds.

STNet (Gatti, Parikh, Paul, Gupta and Mishra, 2024) demonstrated that traditional retrieval systems may require additional information to support sketch-based search, especially when using only sketches is insufficient to express complex concepts. The CSTBIR (Composite Sketch+Text Based Image Retrieval) problem, introduced by them, specifically addresses scenarios where sketches are rough and text serves as a complementary input. They introduced a multimodal transformer-based model for CSTBIR that jointly processes sketches and text to retrieve relevant natural scene images. ARNet (Jiang, Tang, Jiang, Yu and Wu, 2025) proposes an innovative solution to improve Fine-Grained Sketch-Based Image Retrieval (FG-SBIR). It leverages dual weight-sharing networks to optimize the alignment between sketch and image domains, addressing the challenges of feature saturation seen with single-encoder architectures. Instead of using traditional Triplet Loss, ARNet introduces a Contrastive Loss function that enhances intra- and inter-sample alignment and incorporates the Multi-Scale Token Recycling (MSTR) module for Vision Transformers (ViTs), which reuses discarded Patch Tokens, enhancing the model’s ability to capture diverse and semantically rich features from both sketches and images.

Another challenge in retrieval is Zero-Shot Sketch-Based Image Retrieval (ZS-SBIR) (Lyou, Lee, Kim and Lee, 2024; Lin, Li, Li, Hospedales, Song and Qi, 2023), which aims to retrieve images from unseen categories during training. Traditional methods struggle with the high cost of paired sketch-image datasets. To address this, Lyou et al. (2024) propose Modality-Aware Encoders, a framework that aligns sketches and images indirectly through text descriptions. This eliminates the need for paired data during training. Recent research trends highlight the importance of data-free learning (DFL) (Chen, Wang, Xu, Yang, Liu, Shi, Xu, Xu and Tian, 2019), driven by privacy concerns and the high cost of collecting paired sketch-image datasets, as discussed earlier. In this context, it is common to use modality-specific encoders (e.g., trained separately on sketches and images) and transfer them to new tasks without requiring additional supervision (Chaudhuri, Bhunia, Song and Dutta, 2023). *Developing an effective sketch representation mechanism would thus benefit not only SBIR but also data-free scenarios.*

This is the motivation behind our work, which extends a previous study (Federico et al., 2025), where a novel architecture was introduced to capture sketch-specific features for generation and classification tasks. However, that model was not originally designed to produce a compact, global descriptor suitable for retrieval. This limitation motivated us to explore whether the learned representations could be adapted to retrieval settings, while preserving the fine-grained sensitivity and abstraction capabilities. In this paper, we propose a retrieval-oriented adaptation of that architecture to produce discriminative sketch embeddings. Our results, which surpass state-of-the-art methods, suggest that this approach can serve as a strong sketch encoder for retrieval tasks and could play a key role in supporting SBIR and data-free learning approaches.

3 ViSkech-GPT for retrieval

Federico et al. (2025) introduced a network called **ViSketch-GPT**, designed for sketch generation and classification tasks. The architecture consists of a diffusion model for the generative component, followed by a transformer-based encoder-decoder network for refinement. Specifically, after generating a sketch, the encoder of the transformer is provided with the current contextual information for each tile to be refined, while the decoder decodes the encoder’s output into a sequence of tokens. These tokens are then further processed by a VQ-VAE to produce the refined tile. In the classification task, only the encoder is used, where, given an input sketch to classify, the context for each tile is provided, and the resulting CLS tokens for each tile are processed by a final layer to generate a single CLS token for classification.

Following the Sketch Gestalt concept introduced by Lin et al. (2020), they pre-train both the encoder and decoder of the transformer using an increasingly complex completion task. In this task, the model is trained to generate missing tiles in a partially completed sketch.

But the core innovation of ViSketch-GPT lies in how sketches are represented: instead of processing the entire sketch as a single image or as a sequence of strokes, they decompose it into *a sequence of tiles*. For each tile, they extract a *multi-level context* that captures both local and global features, enabling a richer and more structured representation.

In particular, given a sketch S , the algorithm first computes the **signed distance field (SDF)** of the sketch — an alternative and more informative representation commonly used in computer graphics — which, for readability, we define as ϕ_s in which, instead of assigning each pixel a binary value (0 for empty space, 1 for stroke), each pixel is assigned a distance value relative to the sketch (with the stroke considered as the reference). Then, the sketch is represented as a sequence of L tiles extracted from its SDF:

$$S \rightarrow \{l_{\phi_s}^{(1)}, \dots, l_{\phi_s}^{(i-1)}, l_{\phi_s}^{(i)}, \dots, l_{\phi_s}^{(L)}\}$$

Fig. 1: The ViSketch-GPT algorithm first computes the SDF of the sketch (ϕ_s) and subsequently constructs the quadtree.

These tiles, in particular, correspond to the **leaves of a quadtree**, obtained by recursively partitioning the SDF only if a certain tile contains significant information or until a predefined depth is reached (Figure 1).

Finally, for each tile, a so-called *leaf context* $\aleph(l_{\phi_s}^{(i)})$ is extracted, which captures both *global* and *local* information of the corresponding leaf.

The context of a leaf $\aleph(l_{\phi_s}^{(i)})$ is defined as the set of spatial neighbors of the leaf itself and all of its ancestors. Specifically, given the leaf $l_{\phi_s}^{(i)}$, its spatial neighbors will correspond to the 3x3 grid of tiles where the leaf itself is at the center of the grid, and each tile has the same size as the leaf. The subsequent neighbors will be those of the 3x3 grid where the parent of the leaf is at the center, and each tile has the size of the parent. This process continues until the root itself is reached (the top-down view of the sketch). The entire process is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: The algorithm for extracting the informative context of each leaf.

Note that when we build the quadtree, we ensure that *all leaves, regardless of their level, are resized to a fixed resolution*.

Therefore, the final representation of the sketch S will be a sequence of leaf contexts:

$$S \rightarrow \left\{ \aleph \left(l_{\phi_s}^{(1)} \right), \dots, \aleph \left(l_{\phi_s}^{(i-1)} \right), \aleph \left(l_{\phi_s}^{(i)} \right), \dots, \aleph \left(l_{\phi_s}^{(L)} \right) \right\}$$

We will use these *descriptors* to represent the entire sketch. Specifically, the ViSketch-GPT architecture processes each context separately through a Transformer Encoder, extracting a summarizing embedding (CLS token) for each. Therefore, by processing L leaves, L CLS tokens are produced. Finally, these are all processed together by an additional self-attention layer, which generates the final summarizing embedding (another CLS token) (Figure 3), which is used for the retrieval task:

$$\text{Logits, Embedding} = \text{ViSketch-GPT} \left(\aleph \left(l_{\phi_s}^{(1)} \right), \dots, \aleph \left(l_{\phi_s}^{(i)} \right), \dots, \aleph \left(l_{\phi_s}^{(L)} \right) \right)$$

Fig. 3: The ViSketch-GPT architecture adapted to the retrieval task.

To train the model for the retrieval task, a loss function is minimized that combines the classical cross entropy loss for the individual sketch and a triplet loss to ensure that final embeddings are similar to samples of the same class and as distinct as possible to samples belonging to different classes:

$$\mathcal{L} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\text{CrossEntropy}}(\text{Logits}^A) + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{Triplet}}(\text{Embedding}^A, \text{Embedding}^P, \text{Embedding}^N)$$

where A , P , and N represent the anchor, positive, and negative examples, respectively, while α and β are the weights used during training to determine the contribution of each loss term to the final loss.

4 Experiments

To assess the effectiveness of our approach, we evaluated **ViSketch-GPT** (adapted to retrieval) on two datasets: QuickDraw (Jongejan, Rowley, Kawashima, Kim and Fox-Gieg, 2016; Ha and Eck, 2018) and TU-Berlin (Eitz et al., 2012).

4.1 Datasets

Our experiments are conducted initially using the QuickDraw dataset, a large-scale collection of human-drawn sketches originating from the Google game *Quick, Draw!*. In this online game, users were prompted to rapidly produce drawings — each within a 20-second limit — corresponding to predefined categories. The dataset comprises approximately 50 million sketches spanning 345 distinct categories.

Each sketch in QuickDraw is encoded as a sequence of *pen stroke actions*, each defined by a five-dimensional tuple:

$$(\Delta_x, \Delta_y, p_1, p_2, p_3)$$

where:

- Δ_x and Δ_y denote the relative displacement from the previous point in the sketch.
- p_1 is a binary flag indicating whether the pen is in contact with the surface (1) or not (0), thereby controlling line continuity.
- p_2 is a binary value that determines whether the pen is lifted after reaching the current point (1) or remains in contact (0).
- p_3 specifies whether the current point marks the end of the drawing sequence (1) or if it continues (0).

To make the sketches compatible with our framework, each drawing is rendered as an image.

We adopted the preprocessing procedures and dataset splits proposed by Ha and Eck (2018), allocating 70,000 sketches per class for training, 2,500 for validation, and 2,500 for testing. Additionally, to ensure comparability with prior work, we simplified the stroke sequences using the *Ramer-Douglas-Peucker* (RDP) algorithm, constraining the maximum sequence length to 321.

In addition to QuickDraw, we also employed the *TU-Berlin* dataset, which, although smaller in scale, offers higher-quality sketch samples. The TU-Berlin dataset comprises 250 object categories, each represented by 80 human-drawn sketches. Compared to QuickDraw, the sketches in TU-Berlin are typically more refined and detailed.

4.2 Competitors

We conduct a comparative analysis of multiple baseline models following the same procedure of Sketch-BERT:

1. **BiLSTM** (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997): A three-layer bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) model is utilized to assess recognition and retrieval tasks on sequential sketch data. The hidden state dimensionality is set to 512.
2. **Sketch-a-Net** (Yu et al., 2015): A convolutional neural network specifically designed for sketch data.
3. **DSSA** (Song, Yu, Song, Xiang and Hospedales, 2017): This approach extends Sketch-a-Net by incorporating an attention module and a high-order energy triplet loss function.
4. **ResNet** (He, Zhang, Ren and Sun, 2016): A widely used residual neural network architecture in computer vision, primarily designed for image recognition tasks.
5. **TC-Net** (Lin, Fu, Lu, Gong, Xue and Jiang, 2019): A network based on DenseNet (Huang, Liu, Van Der Maaten and Weinberger, 2017), applied to sketch-based image retrieval tasks. We utilize a pre-trained version for classification and retrieval experiments.
6. **Sketch-BERT** (Lin et al., 2020): A BERT-based model, adapted for free-hand sketches, uses BERT’s ability to capture contextual relationships in sequences to interpret sketches as temporal pen strokes.

The training and validation subsets are used for model training, while evaluations are conducted on the test set.

To evaluate the performance of different models, triplet loss and cross-entropy loss are applied to the sketch features extracted from each competitor, with each model serving as the backbone.

4.3 Implementation details

For each sketch, we rendered the image at a resolution of 128x128 and used a maximum quadtree depth of 4, thus processing tiles with a resolution of 32x32. For the Transformer Encoder, we used a hidden size of 256, a depth of 6 and 8 attention heads. The encoder was pre-trained as discussed in the section (3). Finally, to aggregate all the CLS tokens from the various leaves into a single representative token, the final self-attention layer, with a depth of 2, hidden size of 256 and 4 attention heads, is used. For QuickDraw, we used $\alpha = 1, \beta = 1$, while for fine-tuning TU-Berlin, we used $\alpha = 1, \beta = 0.1$.

4.4 Results and discussion

In Table 1, the retrieval results for both datasets under examination are presented. As done by Sketch-BERT, the results on TU-Berlin were obtained by

Methods	QuickDraw			TU-Berlin		
	Top-1	Top-5	mAP	Top-1	Top-5	mAP
Bi-LSTM	70.91	89.52	60.11	31.40	59.60	23.71
Sketch-a-Net	74.88	90.10	65.13	37.25	63.50	26.18
DSSA	78.16	91.04	68.10	38.45	66.10	28.77
ResNet18	80.34	91.71	70.98	41.45	67.10	29.33
ResNet50	82.41	92.52	74.84	51.80	74.45	36.94
TCNet	83.59	92.57	76.38	55.30	79.45	38.78
Sketch-BERT	85.47	93.49	78.87	57.25	81.50	41.54
ViSketch-GPT (our)	96.69	99.92	87.35	67.36	89.40	59.99

Table 1: Performance comparison of various models on the QuickDraw and TU-Berlin datasets. Metrics include Top-1 accuracy, Top-5 accuracy, and mean Average Precision (mAP).

fine-tuning the network trained on QuickDraw. It is evident from the results that our model **far surpasses the various competitors** in each of the 3 metrics (Top1 and Top5 accuracy, Mean Average Precision (mAP)).

It is important to emphasize that **all results shown for the competitors were obtained using all the available data** in QuickDraw, i.e., all 345 classes and 70K examples per class, but **ViSketch-GPT achieved significantly better performance on both QuickDraw and TU-Berlin using only 100 classes and 5K** examples per class, even for the pretraining phase before fine-tuning on TU-Berlin (where we instead used all the available data as done by the competitors). In Table 2, the performance difference obtained by the main competitor Sketch-BERT using different volumes of training data is shown compared to our network, which uses much less.

Models	Top-1 (%)	Top-5 (%)
Sketch-BERT (100 × 5K)	81.91	92.01
Sketch-BERT (200 × 5K)	81.87	92.07
Sketch-BERT (345 × 5K)	82.44	92.13
Sketch-BERT (345 × 70K)	85.47	93.49
ViSketch-GPT (100 × 5K)	96.69	99.92

Table 2: The performance of Sketch-BERT on retrieval task on the QuickDraw dataset after different volumes of training data compared to the performance of ViSketch-GPT which uses much less data.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we extended the ViSketch-GPT architecture — originally designed for sketch generation and classification — to the task of sketch retrieval. Our

proposed method introduces an innovative approach to sketch representation by leveraging a quadtree-based spatial decomposition over Signed Distance Fields (SDFs), combined with a multi-scale context extraction for each tile. This enables the model to effectively capture both local and global features of the sketch.

Experimental results on two widely adopted benchmarks — QuickDraw and TU-Berlin — demonstrate that ViSketch-GPT is not only competitive but significantly outperforms state-of-the-art methods in key retrieval metrics, despite relying on fewer classes and samples during pretraining. This indicates a greater generalization capability compared to existing models.

Furthermore, the architecture proves to be particularly suitable for real-world scenarios characterized by high stylistic variability, uneven sketch quality, and limited supervision, making it a promising candidate for multimodal retrieval, human-computer interaction, and data-free learning tasks.

Nonetheless, one notable limitation of the proposed method lies in its computational footprint: although the model itself is lightweight, it must be instantiated and executed for each leaf node in the quadtree.

Future work will explore extending ViSketch-GPT to cross-modal contexts — e.g., integrating textual or visual inputs — and applying it to zero-shot and few-shot learning settings, to further enhance the model’s flexibility under low supervision.

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